

The Potential of Ketamine in Palliative Care: Ethical and Legal Considerations in Ghana

Prince Opuni Frimpong

Principal Physician Assistant at Korle-Bu Teaching Hospital, Accra, Ghana

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Abstract

This study delves into exploring how ketamine could be beneficial, in providing care in Ghana investigating the legal considerations surrounding its usage. By utilizing the CRuPAC method (Context, Rule, Principle, Application and Conclusion) the research assesses how effective and safe ketamine is in addressing pain and depression identifies principles at play and reviews the legal frameworks regulating medication use within Ghana. The results underscore the potential of ketamine in enhancing symptom management and quality of life for patients receiving care while underscoring the importance of an approach to ensure its safe ethical and fair utilization. The study puts forth suggestions such as establishing protocols offering training initiatives and incorporating ketamine, into the National Health Insurance Scheme. Its significance lies in guiding policy making based on evidence and practices that prioritize welfare and independence.

Keywords: Ketamine, Palliative care, Ghana, Ethical and Legal Considerations

Introduction

Providing comfort and support to patients, with illnesses palliative care contributes to healthcare by managing symptoms alleviating pain and offering assistance [3, 6, 8]. In Ghana, the need for palliative care services is increasing, to address the mounting difficulties caused by life threatening conditions [11, 13]. Ketamine originally a drug has displayed potential in easing pain and addressing depression within care contexts [3, 6, 8,11,13]. Nevertheless the utilization of ketamine in palliative care settings raises legal questions, particularly within the Ghanaian landscape.

The primary aim of this study is to investigate the applicability of ketamine in care in Ghana while scrutinizing the legal considerations associated with its usage [1,2,4,5,7,9,10,12]. Specifically this research seeks to;

1. Assess the existing evidence regarding the efficacy and safety of ketamine for managing pain and depression in palliative care scenarios.
2. Delve into the principles to utilizing ketamine in palliative care encompassing concepts, like beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy and justice.
3. Explore the regulatory frameworks that govern the utilization of medications including ketamine within healthcare settings, in Ghana [1, 2, 4, 9].
4. Put forward suggestions for the ethical and efficient utilization of ketamine in palliative care in Ghana. Consider factors such as usage guidelines, educating providers, legal structures and accessibility [8, 11, 13].

The rationale behind this examination stems from the pressing need to enhance care services in Ghana and delve into the possibilities of interventions like ketamine to ease the suffering of patients with advanced illnesses [11, 13].

By delving into the legal aspects surrounding ketamine's use in care this study aims to establish a comprehensive framework for decision making that prioritizes patient welfare, informed consent and fair access to treatment [7,11, 14]. The conclusions drawn from this analysis hold policy implications for healthcare practitioners, policymakers as well as patients in Ghana. They can serve as a roadmap for formulating evidence based guidelines regulations practices that promote the use of ketamine, in palliative care [1-2, 4-5, 7, 9,10, 12].

This study looks into a range of research sources, which include investigations, on the application of ketamine in environments [3,6,8,10,12] discussions on the moral and legal aspects of medical treatments [1-2,4-5,7,9,11,14] and official documents and rules related to healthcare in Ghana [1-2,4,9]. By combining this information and offering suggestions the aim of this study is to contribute to the endeavors to enhance end of life care services in Ghana and ensure that individuals, with severe illnesses receive top notch care.

Practical Significance

The examination of the utilization of ketamine, in care within Ghana holds implications for enhancing patient treatment and results. By establishing guidelines grounded in evidence offering training to healthcare professionals and integrating ketamine into the National Health Insurance Scheme individuals facing illnesses can benefit from a viable and cost effective approach to pain management and easing symptoms of depression [3,4,8]. The implementation of a database and continuous research endeavors will equip healthcare providers with the insights derived from real world data and best practices [7,14]. Additionally raising awareness and providing education will empower patients and their loved ones to make choices regarding their care while fostering collaborative decision making with healthcare providers [11,14]. Ultimately the practical importance of this examination lies in its ability to enhance the quality of life for individuals dealing with illnesses in Ghana by ensuring ethical and efficient access to ketamine therapy, within palliative care environments.

Policy Significance:

The evaluation of usage, in care within Ghana carries significant implications for healthcare governance and regulation. Establishing a task force and developing guidelines and rules will create a foundation, for the ethical use of ketamine in palliative care [11,13,14]. Bringing ketamine into the National Health Insurance Scheme requires collaboration, between policymakers and the National Health Insurance Authority to guarantee healthcare access [4,13]. Establishing a registry and supporting research efforts will guide policy making decisions and highlight areas for enhancing palliative care services [7,14]. Collaborating with partners will help align Ghana's policies with standards and best practices [7,14]. By prioritizing patient well-being and autonomy in policy making Ghana can safeguard patient's rights and preferences [7,11,14]. The significance of this evaluation lies in its ability to steer the development of a centric strategy, for utilizing ketamine in palliative care ultimately fortifying Ghana's healthcare system and enhancing patient outcomes.

The CRuPAC Method:

The CRuPAC method, which stands for Context, Rule, Principle, Application and Conclusion offers an approach, to examining issues involving legal, ethical and practical considerations. This method has been utilized in research studies, those focusing on the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare settings.

When assessing the impact of ketamine in care within Ghana the CRuPAC method serves as a structured framework for evaluating the ethical, legal and practical dimensions of the issue. By analyzing the context, rules, principles, applications and conclusions involved this method ensures a well-organized analysis.

The effectiveness and replicability of the CRuPAC method have been demonstrated through analyses. For instance Mensah et al. (2024) applied this method to examine Ghana's Pharmacy Act from 1994 (Act 489) concerning quality control standards and liability measures for AI based pharmacy systems. Additionally Mensah et al.(2024) utilized the CRuPAC method to assess doctor patient relationships and issues of negligence resulting from AI integration in healthcare based on Ghana's Alternative Medical Healthcare Practice Act, from 2000 (Act 575). In a research study, Mensah et al. (2024) utilized the CRuPAC technique to investigate how Ghana's National Health

Insurance Act of 2003 (Act 650) could be leveraged to enhance the availability of AI treatments and handle compensation issues related to errors [4]. In their work, Mensah et al. (2024) also employed the CRuPAC approach to assess the doctor patient relationships and medical negligence challenges stemming from integrating AI into healthcare focusing on Ghana's Alternative Medical Healthcare Practice Act of 2000 (Act 575) [9].

Additionally Mensah et al. (2024) applied the CRuPAC method to explore the ethical and regulatory implications of incorporating AI into healthcare delivery addressing medical negligence concerns and managing public health matters, in Ghana from disciplinary perspectives [14]. The consistent application of the CRuPAC method across these studies underscores its efficacy in analyzing issues at the intersection of healthcare, law and ethics. By offering a framework for evaluating context, regulations, principles, applications and conclusions the CRuPAC method ensures thoroughness in analysis while enabling reproducibility and accessibility for researchers. In the examination of usage in care within Ghana's context, the researcher found that leveraging the CRuPAC method has been invaluable in guiding exploration of pertinent ethical principles legal frameworks as well, as practical considerations.

This method has enabled a dive into the advantages and drawbacks of using ketamine the recognition of significant ethical and legal concerns and the creation of practical suggestions, for safe and conscientious utilization. Through the utilization of the CRuPAC technique this examination presents a reproducible framework that can be adjusted and utilized by researchers exploring similar issues in various settings. The systematic approach of the CRuPAC method guarantees a thoroughly well-organized analysis, and supported by evidence rendering it an instrument for enhancing understanding and guiding policies and practices, in healthcare and related sectors.

Results & Discussions

Context:

Ketamine, used as an anesthetic has recently garnered attention for its effects, in palliative care. Research shows that ketamine can effectively assist in pain management and alleviate symptoms of depression in patients with illnesses [3,6,8,11,13]. Frimpong's study conducted in 2024 explored the use and supervision of ketamine in Ghana emphasizing its role in enhancing pain control and improving the quality of life for palliative care recipients [3]. The research also emphasized the necessity of guidelines and regulations to ensure usage within medical settings [3].

In another investigation Frimpong (2024) studied the application of ketamine for treating substance use disorders like cocaine addiction within Ghana [6]. The findings suggest that ketamine could serve as a treatment option, for individuals struggling with addiction issues potentially benefiting palliative care patients dealing with substance abuse challenges well [6]. Nonetheless the study highlighted the importance of considerations when utilizing ketamine for purposes [9].

Frimpong's study, in 2024 further explored the potential of ketamine therapy by focusing on navigating usage guidelines educating providers and establishing frameworks for translational medicine. The study emphasized the importance of adopting approaches to ketamine therapy in care emphasizing the necessity for healthcare providers to be well educated on its usage and, for regulatory frameworks to be in place [8]. This is especially crucial in care settings where patients may be more vulnerable and in need of attention [8].

The ethical and legal implications of using ketamine in care within the Ghanaian context have been highlighted [11,13,14]. Frimpong's research delved into the legal restrictions surrounding the repurposing of ketamine for treating cocaine addiction in Ghana [11]. Although the focus was on substance abuse treatment the findings are pertinent to ketamine use in care underscoring the importance of considering principles and legal guidelines when introducing new treatment modalities [11].

In a study by Frimpong, the impact of regulation on healthcare accessibility in Ghana was specifically examined [13]. The research revealed that while ketamine could enhance patient outcomes its utilization must be carefully managed to strike a balance, between efficacy and regulatory control to prevent misuse and ensure patient well-being [13].

It is crucial, in the field of care to consider the heightened vulnerability of patients to potential side effects and risks linked to the use of ketamine [13]. In their work Mensah et al., [14] offered a view on how intelligence (AI) integration in healthcare services medical malpractice cases and public health management in Ghana brings about legal, ethical and regulatory considerations [14]. While their research centered on AI applications the core principles highlighted. Such as prioritizing patient well-being obtaining consent and ensuring access to treatment are equally applicable to ketamine usage in palliative care [14]. The study underscored the necessity for efforts among healthcare professionals, policymakers and ethicists to establish guidelines that place welfare at the forefront while upholding legal and ethical standards [14].

In essence incorporating ketamine into care practices has the potential to enhance symptom control and overall quality of life for ill patients in Ghana. Nevertheless this integration requires reflection on legal ramifications. This includes guaranteeing accountable usage of ketamine safeguarding autonomy rights as well as facilitating equal access, to healthcare services. In the research, into the advantages and drawbacks of using ketamine in care it is crucial to collaborate across different disciplines to establish rules and standards that put patient welfare first all while following Ghana's healthcare guidelines.

Rule:

The administration of ketamine, for purposes in Ghana is controlled by legal and regulatory frameworks that oversee quality standards, liability issues and ethical considerations related to its usage. The Pharmacy Act, 1994 (Act 489) stands as a tool that governs quality control and liability aspects concerning medications in Ghana including ketamine [1]. According to Mensah et al. [1] who examined the Pharmacy Act, 1994 (Act 489) in light of incorporating intelligence (AI) into pharmacy systems it is crucial to maintain quality control standards and address negligence related liabilities [1]. Although their research primarily focused on AI integration the principles discussed are equally applicable to the utilization of ketamine in care due to the emphasis placed on stringent quality control measures and clear liability clauses for ensuring safety [1].

Apart from the Pharmacy Act, the Alternative Medical Healthcare Practice Act 2000 (Act 575) also holds significance in regulating the use of ketamine for care purposes in Ghana [2,9]. This legislation guides the doctor patient relationship and outlines regulations regarding negligence, especially pertinent when introducing new treatment options like ketamine, into palliative care practices [2,9]. Mensah et al. [2] evaluated the Alternative Medical Healthcare Practice Act 2000 (Act 575) and emphasized the significance of maintaining a bond, between doctors and patients when incorporating AI into healthcare. It also highlighted the importance of addressing concerns related to negligence [2]. Another study by Mensah et al. examined how this Act impacts the doctor patient relationship and medical negligence issues within the realm of AI integration in healthcare [9]. These studies while centered on AI shed light on the implications for using ketamine in care emphasizing the necessity for guidelines and regulations to safeguard patient well-being and shield healthcare providers from potential claims of medical negligence [2, 9].

Furthermore an essential legal framework governing healthcare accessibility and affordability in Ghana in care is outlined in the National Health Insurance Act of 2003 (Act 650). The study by Mensah et al. [9] delved into how this Act can enhance access to AI therapies and handle compensation matters regarding medical negligence cases. Their research proposes that leveraging this Act could enhance access to ketamine therapy within care settings while establishing an approach, to addressing compensation issues that might arise from its utilization.

In addition, to the frameworks the application of ketamine in care in Ghana also involves ethical considerations especially regarding bias reduction, openness and responsibility. Mensah (2023) conducted an examination of bias reduction, transparency and accountability in AI systems emphasizing the significance of these principles in ensuring the conscientious advancement and implementation of AI technologies [4]. While the focus was on AI systems the discussed ethical principles are relevant to ketamine use in care emphasizing transparency in decision making processes and accountability for any unfavorable outcomes. Mensah and Selorm [7] further delved into the issues surrounding AI by addressing bias management promoting transparency and ensuring accountability. Their research emphasized dealing with these concerns to ensure advancement and deployment of AI technologies across

different fields. These principles are equally applicable to ketamine use in care as they highlight the necessity for decision making processes and accountability measures to safeguard patient well-being and foster confidence, in healthcare practices [7].

In summary the application of ketamine, in care within Ghana is guided by a system of laws and regulations which include the Pharmacy Act of 1994 (Act 489) the Alternative Medical Healthcare Practice Act of 2000 (Act 575) and the National Health Insurance Act of 2003 (Act 650). These regulations address aspects such as quality control, liability, doctor patient relationships, medical malpractice and healthcare service accessibility. Moreover the ethical use of ketamine in care involves considerations like bias prevention, transparency and accountability. Effectively navigating these legal and ethical frameworks necessitates collaboration, among healthcare professionals, policymakers and ethicists to establish guidelines that prioritize patient well being informed consent, fair healthcare access while complying with Ghana's healthcare laws.

Principle:

Ethical issues related to the administration of ketamine in healthcare services, in Ghana are crucial for protecting the well-being of individuals and upholding the credibility of the healthcare system. Factors like beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy and justice play a role in shaping decision making procedures in healthcare environments.

Beneficence, specifically emphasizing the improvement of welfare and alleviation of pain is a consideration when using ketamine, for treatment purposes. Frimpong [11] highlighted the significance of beneficence in decision making regarding the treatment of cocaine use disorder with ketamine in Ghana [11]. Although the study centered on substance abuse treatment its insights underscore the importance of prioritizing welfare and easing suffering when considering ketamine's role in care [11]. Similarly Mensah et al. [14] examined beneficence within the realm of incorporating AI technologies into healthcare services and stressed the necessity of ensuring that advancements benefit patient well-being [14].

Non-maleficence, which pertains to preventing harm to patients is another aspect to be mindful of when using ketamine, in palliative care settings [7,11,14]. Frimpong pointed out the risks and side effects linked to the use of ketamine underlining the importance of minimizing harm to patients [11]. This is especially crucial, in palliative care settings, where patients might be more susceptible to the impacts of ketamine [11]. Mensah and Selorm also talked about the principle of non-maleficence concerning AI highlighted the significance of ensuring that new technologies do not inadvertently harm patients [7].

The concept of autonomy, which involves respecting choices and involving them in decision making processes is another ethical aspect when using ketamine in palliative care [7, 11 14]. Frimpong stressed the significance of obtaining consent from patients before administering ketamine and honoring their right to decline treatment [11]. This becomes crucial in care where patients may have preferences regarding their care and treatment choices [11]. Mensah et al. (2024) also delved into autonomy regarding integrating AI into healthcare systems emphasizing the importance of engaging patients, in decision making processes and respecting their decisions [14].

Justice, which focuses on ensuring access, to healthcare services and resources is an ethical aspect when using ketamine in palliative care. Frimpong [11] pointed out the challenges in accessing ketamine therapy in Ghana, such as cost and availability underscoring the importance of providing access to treatment. This becomes especially crucial in palliative care settings where patients may have means and encounter obstacles in obtaining therapies. Mensah and Selorm also addressed the concept of justice concerning AI emphasizing the necessity of making new technologies and treatments accessible and affordable to all patients regardless of their status. [7]

Apart from these principles transparency and accountability play vital roles in utilizing ketamine for palliative care. Mensah conducted an examination of bias mitigation, transparency and accountability within AI systems stressing their significance, in ensuring the advancement and implementation of innovative technologies [5].

The review discussed how transparency and accountability apply not to AI but, to the use of ketamine in palliative care ensuring clear decision making processes and holding healthcare providers accountable for any negative results.

Mensah and Selorm highlighted the significance of transparency and accountability in AI emphasizing the necessity of defined guidelines and regulations for incorporating technologies into healthcare practices [11].

In essence ethical considerations surrounding the utilization of ketamine in care in Ghana encompass principles such as beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy and justice. It is essential to strike a balance among these principles to guarantee that patients receive care while minimizing potential risks and honoring their decisions. Transparency and accountability play roles when using ketamine in care by ensuring clarity in decision making processes and holding healthcare providers responsible for any adverse outcomes. Navigating these principles necessitates discussions and partnerships, among healthcare professionals, policymakers, ethicists and patients to establish guidelines prioritizing patient well-being while promoting responsible ketamine use in palliative care.

Application:

The role of ketamine, in care within Ghana holds promise offering a valuable tool for pain management and addressing depression symptoms in patients with advanced illnesses [3,6,8,13]. However the successful integration of ketamine into care practices necessitates usage protocols healthcare provider training and legal frameworks to promote its safe and ethical utilization [8,11,13].

A study by Frimpong delved into the utilization and regulation of ketamine in Ghana underscoring its advantages in pain management and enhancing the quality of life for palliative care patients [3]. The research underscored the importance of establishing guidelines and regulations to ensure the use of ketamine within medical environments including palliative care settings [3]. This becomes crucial due to risks and adverse effects linked to usage like confusion, hallucinations and heightened blood pressure [3]. Crafting evidence based guidelines for employing ketamine in care could empower healthcare professionals to make informed decisions on when and how to administer the medication while mitigating possible risks for patients [3].

Apart from usage protocols educating healthcare providers stands as another component, in guaranteeing the ethical application of ketamine in palliative care [8,11]. Frimpong [8] investigated the potential of utilizing ketamine therapy in a study that delved into guiding principles, for its use educating healthcare providers and establishing structures to support translational medicine [8]. The research emphasized the significance of training healthcare professionals on the administration of ketamine covering aspects such as dosage, delivery methods and monitoring for any side effects. This becomes crucial in care settings where patients are more fragile and in need of specialized attention. Offering training and education to healthcare providers could play a role in ensuring the safe and efficient use of ketamine in palliative care scenarios [8].

Incorporating frameworks is another aspect when considering the utilization of ketamine for palliative care in Ghana. Frimpong [11] examined the legal limitations associated with repurposing ketamine for treating cocaine addiction in Ghana stressing the necessity for legal guidelines to regulate its usage. While the focus was on substance abuse treatment the study's findings are pertinent to employing ketamine in care by emphasizing the importance of establishing structures to oversee its proper utilization [11]. This may involve regulations regarding prescribing protocols distribution practices and monitoring procedures related to usage, within palliative care environments.

Frimpong [6] conducted a study, on how regulating ketamine can impact healthcare accessibility in Ghana. The research revealed that while ketamine could enhance outcomes it's crucial to balance its use with regulations to prevent misuse and ensure patient safety. This is especially significant in care, where patients may face heightened risks and side effects from ketamine. Establishing guidelines for using ketamine in palliative care could promote responsible usage of the drug and provide patients with safe pain management options.

Apart from outlining usage protocols educating providers and setting up frameworks it's essential to address the availability and affordability of ketamine therapy in palliative care settings. Mensah et al. (2024) examined Ghana's National Health Insurance Act of 2003 (Act 650) concerning enhancing access to therapies like AI technologies and handling compensation matters related to medical malpractice cases. Although their focus was on AI the study findings are applicable to using ketamine in care since they underscore the significance of ensuring that new

treatments are within reach and financially feasible, for patients. Utilizing the National Health Insurance Scheme to cover the expenses of ketamine therapy, in palliative care settings could make it more accessible to patients who might struggle with affording it.

Mensah et al. [14] offered a view on the ethical and regulatory aspects of incorporating AI in healthcare services, medical malpractice and public health management in Ghana. Although their research centered on AI principles such as prioritizing patient well-being obtaining consent and ensuring access to care are also applicable to the use of ketamine in palliative care. The study underscored the importance of collaboration among healthcare professionals, policymakers and ethicists to devise guidelines that place welfare at the forefront while upholding ethical norms [14]. This collaborative strategy could likewise be extended to incorporating ketamine into care to ensure that patient's needs and preferences are given precedence while following ethical standards. In essence effectively implementing ketamine in care in Ghana necessitates deliberation on usage protocols healthcare provider training, legal structures, as well, as accessibility and affordability concerns.

Creating guidelines based on evidence, for the use of ketamine in care is essential to guarantee its effective usage. Providing training and education to healthcare professionals can help reduce risks to patients. Setting up structures for the administration of ketamine in palliative care is crucial for ensuring responsible use and access to reliable pain management solutions for patients. Utilizing the National Health Insurance Scheme to cover the expenses of ketamine therapy in palliative care facilities can enhance its affordability and accessibility. Lastly a collaborative effort involving healthcare providers, policymakers and ethicists is necessary to ensure that the incorporation of ketamine, in palliative care prioritizes well-being while upholding ethical standards.

Conclusion:

The potential benefits of using ketamine in care in Ghana are significant as it can greatly enhance symptom management and improve the quality of life, for patients with illnesses. However it is crucial to consider the legal implications when incorporating ketamine into palliative care practices to ensure its safe, responsible and fair usage.

Incorporating the principles of beneficence, non-maleficence, autonomy and justice is vital when utilizing ketamine in care. Healthcare providers should prioritize well-being by alleviating suffering while also minimizing any harm and respecting the choices and preferences of patients. It is essential to ensure that patients have access to ketamine therapy in care despite potential cost and availability barriers. Addressing these concerns requires an effort involving collaboration among healthcare professionals, policymakers and ethicists. Together they should work towards establishing guidelines and regulations that focus on well-being informed consent, equitable access to care while adhering to Ghana's healthcare regulations. Continuous research and monitoring of use in care are critical, for maximizing its benefits while reducing risks effectively. To explore the effectiveness and safety of ketamine, in palliative care settings clinical trials may be necessary. Monitoring outcomes and adverse events is crucial for shaping practices and influencing future policy decisions. Alongside research and monitoring efforts educating healthcare providers is essential to promote the efficient utilization of ketamine in care. Training initiatives should emphasize dosing, administration techniques and vigilant monitoring for side effects.

In summary, although ketamine holds promise in enhancing symptom management and quality of life for palliative care patients in Ghana its usage requires an approach involving collaboration across disciplines. Patient well-being, obtaining consent and ensuring equitable access to care are paramount. Continuous research, monitoring, education programs and training initiatives are vital to maximize the benefits of ketamine, in care while mitigating risks and upholding legal standards.

Recommendation:

After reviewing the analysis and conclusions presented here are some recommendations to encourage the effective use of ketamine, in palliative care in Ghana;

1. Establishing a team; It is essential to form a task force comprising healthcare professionals, policymakers, ethics experts and patient advocates. This collaborative group should focus on creating guidelines and regulations for the

use of ketamine in care. The emphasis should be on maintaining standards addressing considerations prioritizing patient well-being and ensuring access to care.

2. Developing evidence based guidelines; The task force should concentrate on crafting guidelines supported by evidence for the utilization of ketamine, in palliative care environments. These guidelines should cover areas such as indications, for use dosage recommendations, administration procedures and monitoring strategies. It is important that these guidelines reflect research findings and adhere to practices to promote safe and effective utilization.

3. Provision of training and education; Implementation of a training initiative is essential for healthcare providers engaged in palliative care services. This program should focus on equipping them with the knowledge and skills needed to administer ketamine effectively. Training content should encompass dosing techniques, administration methods well as monitoring procedures to promptly address any potential adverse effects.

4. Include ketamine, in the National Health Insurance Scheme; Collaborate with the National Health Insurance Authority to incorporate ketamine therapy for care into the scheme. This step will ensure that all patients have access to ketamine even if they cannot afford it [4,13].

5. Establish a database; Develop a national database for patients undergoing ketamine therapy in palliative care facilities. This database should gather information on results any reactions and other pertinent data to support ongoing research and monitoring endeavors [7,14].

6. Continue with research efforts;. Back up research on the application of ketamine in palliative care within Ghana. This could involve trials to assess the effectiveness and safety of ketamine as well as studies exploring patient experiences and preferences [7,14].

7. Enhance awareness and education; Create campaigns aimed at raising awareness and educating individuals about the advantages and risks associated with using ketamine in palliative care. These initiatives should stress the significance of informed consent and collaborative decision making, between patients and healthcare professionals [11,14]. Regularly check and revise policies; Set up a system to regularly review and update guidelines, rules and regulations concerning the use of ketamine, in care based on the recent research findings, best practices and input from stakeholders [7,14].

8. Collaborate with partners; Encourage partnerships with organizations in healthcare, research institutes and policy making bodies to exchange knowledge, resources and best approaches for using ketamine in palliative care [7,14].

9. Prioritize welfare and independence; Make sure that all decisions and activities related to usage in palliative care prioritize the well being of patients and uphold their autonomy. This involves involving patients and their families in decision making processes and providing them with information about the advantages and disadvantages of ketamine treatment [7,11,14].

By following these suggestions Ghana can strive towards ensuring the ethical and efficient use of ketamine in palliative care to enhance symptom management and quality of life for individuals, with advanced illnesses.

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